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EXPÉRIMENTONS LA PROTOHISTOIRE
DIALOGUES INTERDISCIPLINAIRES

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4 juin 2021, Institut d'Art et d'Archéologie, Paris

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4 juin 2021, Institut d'Art et d'Archéologie, Paris

sous la modération de Haris Procopiou (Prof. Univ. Paris 1)

décembre 2021

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AN EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH TO THE PROPERTIES OF SHEEP DUNG AS A POT FIRING FUEL AND IDENTIFICATION OF ITS USE IN ARCHAEOLOGICAL CONTEXTS

Mike Copper, Gregg Griffin and Cathy Batt

Abstract: In contrast to other elements of the ceramic *chaîne opératoire*, the fuels used to fire pots in prehistory, and their relative advantages and disadvantages, are poorly understood. Given that animal dung would have been a potential fuel widely available to potters in Europe during the Neolithic and Bronze Age, a series of experiments was undertaken at the University of Bradford in the spring of 2021 to investigate the properties and archaeological signatures of dried sheep dung for firing pottery in comparison to wood and peat. As a result of these experiments, we suggest ways that the use of dung as fuel may be identified on archaeological sites.

Key-words: Dung, Pottery, Firing, Fuel, Prehistory

Résumé : Contrairement aux autres éléments de la chaîne opératoire céramique, les combustibles utilisés pour la cuisson des pots pendant la préhistoire, ainsi que leurs avantages et inconvénients relatifs, sont mal connus. Étant donné que les crottes d'animaux auraient été un combustible potentiel largement disponible pour les potiers en Europe au cours du Néolithique et de l'Âge du Bronze, une série d'expérimentations a été entreprise à l'Université de Bradford au printemps 2021. L'objectif était d'étudier les propriétés et les signatures archéologiques des crottins de mouton séchés pour la cuisson des poteries en comparaison avec le bois et la tourbe. À la suite de ces expériences, nous suggérons des moyens permettant d'identifier l'utilisation de crottes d'animaux, et surtout de crottins de moutons, comme combustible sur les sites archéologiques.

Mots-clés : Crottins, Poterie, Cuisson, Combustibles, Préhistoire

INTRODUCTION

Throughout most of prehistory pottery in northern and Atlantic Europe appears to have been open fired. Current evidence suggests that pottery kilns first appeared in northern France in the late 2nd or early 1st millennium BC, though in Britain and Ireland the open firing of pots, probably in pits, depressions or semi-enclosed structures, appears to have continued until the late 1st millennium BC (Morris 1994). Indeed, in some regions, including parts of northern Scotland (Holleyman 1947), traditions of open fired pottery, including pots

fired on the domestic hearth, lasted well into the historical era. While the open firing of pottery continues in many parts of the world today, and is strongly bound up with other economic and social practices (Winterhalder *et al.* 1974; Sillar 2000; Gosselain 2010; 2016), the techniques used vary widely, meaning that ethnographic research is of limited value for ascertaining how pots were fired in prehistory.

A particular issue for archaeologists relates to the fuels used. Available fuels in northern and western Europe would have included wood, peat,

seaweed and dried animal dung, each of which has its own particular characteristics. A series of informal experiments undertaken by one of the present authors (Copper 2019) indicated that peat, a fuel widely used in Europe into the 20th century (Steensberg 1940, Holleyman 1947), has properties that make it suitable for use as a pot firing fuel. Temperatures in a peat fire rise and fall gradually and, in comparison to wood fires, peat fires are relatively easy to manage. Indeed, peat continues to be used for heating and culinary purposes in Europe today, though its social status has varied through time (Vésteinsson and Simpson 2004 ; Håseth *et al.* 2015). Peat, however, is an unevenly distributed resource and is hard to collect and dry. Like peat, but in contrast to wood, dung burns gradually and evenly, yet unlike peat it is a rapidly renewed resource that would have been universally available to early farmers in Europe. As such, it is possible that dung was used as a pot-firing fuel in prehistory. To test this possibility, our experiments were therefore designed to discover:

1. Whether sheep dung could indeed have been used to fire pots. (Sheep dung was chosen for this experiment in preference to other types of dung because: a) published data on sheep dung firings is very sparse in comparison to other fuels, b) sheep dung is easily dried and collected, even in northwest Europe, meaning that it would have been a potentially attractive resource in prehistory, and c) sheep dung is widely available in the area in which the experiments were undertaken.)
2. What the key characteristics of a dung firing are from the potter's point of view.
3. How archaeologists can identify the use of dung as a fuel (especially for pot firing) in archaeological contexts.

PREVIOUS ETHNOGRAPHIC AND EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The use of dung for firing pottery, often in combination with other fuels, is a widespread practice (Arnold 1985, p. 30-31; Sillar 2000). Ethnoarchaeological reports on firings employing *only* dung, however, are very limited (Colton 1951; Shepard 1956, p. 78 and fig. p. 4 and 5; Woods 1984; Krause 1985; Livingstone Smith 2001). In addition, little experimental work has taken place on dung fuels (Sidoroff 2019: being a rare exception). Indeed, the present authors are not aware of any experimental work using unmixed sheep dung. Noting that it is hard to assess the properties of different fuels due to the fact that they are often combined, A. Livingstone Smith categorises fuels more generally as 'light' or 'heavy' (Livingstone Smith 2007, p. 159) and notes that it is hard to correlate the thermal characteristics of a firing, including maximum temperatures, with the fuel used, though dung is often associated with longer firing times (Livingstone Smith 2007, p. 165-166). Longer firing times also tend to correlate with longer 'soaking times' (the time during which the pots remain over 700 °C). As a result of these issues, there is clearly a requirement for more focussed experimental work addressing the properties of dung as a pot-firing fuel in its own right.

An additional problem with much previous research is the limited use made of thermocouples. O. Gosselain (Gosselain 1992, p. 256) has noted that temperatures may vary by up to 300 °C across a single pot. As such, researchers using a single thermocouple (Colton 1951; Woods 1984), will be able to gain only a partial picture of the nature of the firing. Maximum temperatures reported by previous researchers include 552 °C to 689 °C for experimental firings using camel dung (Sidoroff 2019); 755 °C (Rye 1981, tabl. 3) and c. 900 °C

(Shepard 1956, fig. 4) for ethnographically recorded firings containing dung mixed with other fuels; and 885 °C for a firing using only sheep dung (Colton 1951, p. 75). Fortunately, experimental archaeology is ideally place to address this lack of detail.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

THE PRODUCTION OF POTS

All of the pots used in our experiments were made from a fine, grey Gault clay dug by hand in the village of Harlington, 60 km north of London. The clay was mixed with coarse, lime-free sand at a ratio of two parts clay to one part sand. All pots were dried indoors over several weeks and shrinkage rates of around 5 % were recorded on small test strips of the same paste.

Each of our programmed firings contained three vessels:

1. An undecorated, small vessel measuring 8 cm in diameter, 5 cm in height and with walls 1 cm thick. The purpose of these thick-walled vessels was to ascertain how thorough the firings had been through macroscopic analysis of cross-sections of the pots after firing.
2. A replica of a Chalcolithic/Early Bronze Age 'Low Carinated All Over Cord' Beaker measuring 14 cm in diameter, 12 cm in height and with walls of around 5 mm thickness (fig. 1). Some of these vessels were slipped with fine grey Gault clay from Harlington and others with iron-rich red boulder clay from Orkney. The flaring rims and sharp carinations of these vessels were deliberately chosen to present stress points that would likely exhibit damage if temperature rises and falls were not even and gradual.
3. An undecorated, medium-sized vessel of the same shape as the larger pots, measuring 10 cm in diameter, 9 cm in height and with

walls around 5 mm thick. These vessels were unslipped to allow us to compare the vessel colours with the slipped larger vessels.

In all, we undertook seven programmed firings. A further, unplanned eighth dung firing with a single pot was undertaken to test observations made during the earlier firings. We also undertook a series of firings that contained no pots at all in order to generate extra data relating to the effects of the firing on the firing pit itself. All of the firings took place in the same rectangular pit measuring 50 cm x 60 cm at the base and 70 cm x 80 cm at the surface. The pit was 35 cm deep (fig. 2).

None of the firings occupied the whole pit. Instead, three types of structure were constructed on the flat bottom:

- Type 1: A ring of firebricks placed vertically with small gaps between the bricks to allow air to enter the fire while retaining the fuel in place (fig. 2).
- Type 2: A ring of firebricks placed on their sides. In this type of structure the fuel needed to be 'mounded up' over the pots.
- Type 3: Larger pieces of wood arranged around the pots with lighter pieces of wood placed over the vessels themselves.

Fig. 1: Application of impressed cord decoration on a replica Beaker for the project. Credit M. Copper.

Fig. 2: Type 1 firing structure during the first peat firing with thermocouple leads visible. Credit G. Griffin.

In order to prevent damage resulting from thermal shock, additional fuel was added to the firing when there was a danger that the hot pots would become exposed to the cold air too early.

In all of the firings the pots were pre-heated to 240 °C in a domestic oven. This was done to ensure consistency between firings. Gradual heating is essential in order to avoid thermal shock (rapid changes in temperature) that can cause cracking or spalling of the pots. After pre-heating, the pots were placed upside down on small ceramic supports above a bed of hot embers before more fuel was added to the fire. The pots were inverted in order that the more fragile rims would remain in the hot ash after the firing, allowing them to cool more gradually than the bases and thereby

reducing the risk of cracking due to thermal shock. After the fire reached its maximum temperature all pots were allowed to cool to 40 °C before being removed.

Temperatures were recorded with five thermocouples placed at different points in the fire. Thermocouple Lead 1 was placed at the base of the fire, Lead 2 was placed to the side of the fire at above 20 cm from the base, Lead 3 was placed in the centre of the fire 20 cm from the base, Lead 4 was placed inside the largest pot of each firing, and Lead 5 was placed above the inverted base of this pot. In addition, a BTMeter BT-1500 non-contact infrared thermometer (-50 °C - 1500 °C) was used to measure the surface temperatures of each vessel when possible.

Following the first two firings using peat, the pit was re-lined with fresh soil. The reason for this was to ensure that the properties of the soil to be analysed resulted only from the effects of the peat fire with no contamination from other fuels. Likewise, after the two wood firings the pit was again relined with fresh soil before the dung firing was undertaken. Soil samples were taken at several points on the pit base and sides before each change of soil/fuel.

Three types of fuel were used in our experiments:

1. Two firings were undertaken using peat cut in Caithness in the far north of Scotland.
2. Two firings made use of well-seasoned ash wood.
3. Three programmed firings and one unplanned additional firing made use of sheep dung collected from meadows around the village of Lothersdale in the county of North Yorkshire. The dung was collected in the summer of 2020 and dried over the winter of 2020/2021. The pieces of dung varied in size from that of a table tennis ball to small pellets and dust. The different shapes of the dung pieces aided in the construction of the fire.

KEY RESULTS

Peat firings

High temperatures (up to 842 °C) and the longest soaking times (up to two hours) of all of our experiments were obtained in the peat fires. Temperatures in the peat fires also rose and fell more gradually than in the wood or dung firings. A significant problem with peat firing, which also affects wood firings, is that the fuel burns down to a fine ash, which remains hot for several hours. As a result, the bases of the inverted pots are exposed to the cool air while the rims remain in the hot

ash. This results in temperature differences of up to 300 °C across a single pot, which greatly increases the risk of cracking. In this regard, the Type 1 firing structures proved better than the Type 2 structures as the latter made it harder to prevent the fuel from falling away from the pots during the hottest phases of the firing.

Wood firings

High temperatures (up to 936 °C) were also attained in our wood firings, though soaking times were shorter than with peat. The wood fires were also harder to control, while temperatures rose and fell rapidly and varied significantly between different parts of the fire, in one case resulting in catastrophic failure of the larger and smaller vessels. Like peat, wood also burns down to a fine ash, meaning that the thermal profile across a single pot can be up to 300 °C during cooling.

Sheep dung firings

The sheep dung fuel exhibited the fastest temperature rises and falls of all our experiments and, on average, soaking times were shorter. Despite this, all of the pots fired well. Significantly, during our additional eighth firing (fig. 3) we attained a much higher temperature (933 °C) and longer soaking time (roughly one hour) than with the earlier dung firings. This was almost certainly the result of the experience gained during the earlier experiments and emphasises the often-underestimated importance of acquired skill for the success of such activities. This observation also demonstrates that varying experimental parameters is not, on its own, sufficient for understanding the efficacy of different techniques. Importantly, unlike peat and wood, sheep dung does not burn down to a fine ash. Instead, the pieces of dung largely maintain their shape after combustion, forming a 'blanket' that insulates the

Fig. 3: Temperatures recorded from three thermocouples during our eight firing (the fourth dung firing), which contained a single pot. ‘Thermo Lead 2’ was placed on the bottom of the pit, Thermo Lead 4’ inside the inverted pot and ‘Thermo Lead 5’ above the base of the pot. Credit G. Griffin.

pots as they cool (fig. 4). As a result, while the pots in a dung fire may cool more rapidly than those in a peat or wood fire, they do so much more evenly. This significantly reduces the risk of cracking in the latter stages of firing. Dung-fired pots also exhibited little ‘fire clouding’ (the presence of dark patches of carbon on the pots resulting from the presence of smoky fragments of fuel during the later stages of firing).

POST-FIRING ANALYSIS

Our post-firing analysis focused on determining if it was possible to identify what fuels were used in a pottery firing based on analysis of the firing environment, ashes, and the surface and fabrics of the pots. The analysis of soils, combustion residues and pottery entailed careful collection and preparation of sample material. It was particularly important to consider the most effective sampling and analytical methods, including choice of soil and combustion residue samples as well as analysis of pottery fragments,

as these would need to match those that could be carried out on archaeological material (Peters and Batt 2002; Braadbaart *et al.* 2012). This is where the union of experimental archaeology and analytical science is most beneficial: developing methods that can be tested in an iterative process in an analogous setting without risking damage to, or loss of, historically sensitive archaeological material (Braadbaart *et al.* 2009). In this way, experimental archaeology can indicate how new data may be attained from archaeological features previously thought to have little interpretive value (Braadbaart *et al.* 2017). Our experiments aim to contribute to the development and application of sampling strategies and analytical methodologies that will create a more comprehensive understanding of fuel use and the role of fuel in the production of artefacts. Furthermore, experimental approaches such as those presented here have applications beyond the identification of combustion residues (Entwistle *et al.* 1998; Entwistle and Abrahams 2010) and can be used in the interpretation of other practices.

For our project, the chosen analytical methods used were SEM/EDS (scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive spectroscopy) and magnetic susceptibility. These methods are both non-destructive and complementary. Analysis of elemental composition can aid in understanding the magnetic properties of the sample, and *vice versa*. These analytical results are also very easily bolstered by adding additional chemical approaches such as pH and phosphate analysis. XRF (X-ray fluorescence) could be substituted for SEM/EDS, allowing analysis to take place in the field to create results in real time on an archaeological excavation. Though this substitution would lose the benefit of the magnified images available from SEM, it would offer similar analytical data.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS, AIMS, AND OBJECTIVES

The analytical phase of the project aimed to answer the following questions.

- Are there significant differences in the elemental composition or magnetic signatures between the fuel types?
- Are there any markers present within the combustion residues or within the fabric of the pottery that can be used to identify which fuel was used in the firing?
- Is it possible to determine what sort of fuel was used to fire an ancient pot discovered during an excavation?

These aims were addressed by:

- Reviewing existing academic literature on dung firing.

Fig. 4: The pieces of dung maintain their form after combustion, insulating the cooling pots and reducing the risk of damage from thermal shock. Credit M. Copper.

- Comparing and contrasting the results of each firing.
- Analysing the firing site and residual ash in order to identify features that may help to identify the use of dung in archaeological contexts.

METHODS

All the pottery samples were cross-sectioned to identify how well they had fired. This cross sectioning was undertaken using a Dremel rotary tool with a diamond blade. All of the experimental vessels that were cross-sectioned exhibited light coloured internal and external surfaces, indicating that they had been fired in an oxidizing atmosphere. While darker areas were observed within the cores of the pot walls on all three vessels (fig. 5), indicating that the firing had not fully combusted all of the organic matter in the clay, these were more extensive in the case of the dung-fired pot. However, even in this latter case, it was clear that the vessel had been fully fired. It should also be noted that our eighth firing showed that temperatures and soaking times similar to those obtained with peat and wood can be attained with dung once experience has been gained in managing the firing.

Following macroscopic analysis, all of the samples were broken down and then pulverised using a mortar and pestle. To ensure that the grain size was homogenised, each sample was passed through a series of sieves from 2 mm progressing to 500 μm . Approximately 500 g of each sieved sample was retained in an archive for potential further work (Etiégni and Campbell 1991).

In addition to the pottery firing experiments using different fuels, a control sample of pottery of the same fabric as the experimental pots was prepared using a muffle furnace with a controlled temperature to see the effects of firing the clay without any contamination from the fuel. This provided an opportunity to analyse a fired pot that has not been exposed to any outside inclusions from the volatilising, pyrolysis and combustion of a fuel source. It can be assumed that any differences in the results between the laboratory-produced control sample and the samples that have been fired using dung, peat or wood will be due to factors associated with the combustion of fuel. In addition, any differences between the wood, dung or peat-fired samples will most likely be due to the variation in fuel source.

Fig. 5: Cross-sections of medium-sized vessels from wood, dung and peat firings, with contrast exaggerated to highlight darker cores (Scale = 5 cm). Credit M. Copper and G. Griffin.

Magnetic Susceptibility

The magnetic susceptibility of all sample material was measured. To achieve a robust dataset, 3 x 10 cm³ pots were filled for each sample to be measured on a Bartington MS2B magnetic susceptibility bridge. Each sample pot was filled with homogenous material that had been sieved to ensure a uniform grain size to limit anomalous inclusions and to increase the reliability of the data (Blaha *et al.* 2008). Each sample was measured three times, zeroing the machine between every reading, and all procedures were followed as set out in the equipment operation manual (Bartington Instruments 1995). The mass specific magnetic susceptibility and percentage of frequency dependence were then calculated. These were subsequently used to determine if there were significant differences between the magnetic susceptibility data from the various fuels that would allow us to identify fuel type from archaeological material associated with pottery firing.

SEM/EDS

The SEM/EDS provides a magnified image of the sample material as well as quantification of the elemental composition (Goldstein *et al.* 2003). A 12.5 mm aluminium pedestal with double-sided Leit carbon adhesive backing was coated with each sample type. This was achieved by pressing the adhesive-coated pedestal into a tray of sieved homogenous sample material.

Each sample was analysed using the SEM/EDS and an image for each sample was captured, showing the material magnified 300 X. Using this image, areas were then selected for further analysis using spot or area analysis features within Aztec software. A spectroscopic scan of the selected area was analysed and any further areas of interest were pinpointed. Aztec software

indicates the abundances of all elements present within each scan. The SEM/EDS is very useful in archaeological applications, especially when employed as part of a 'toolkit' approach (Ponting 2004).

RESULTS/DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis show differences between the samples that are associated with different fuels. The difference in elemental trends associated with combustion residue materials can be attributed to the composition of the fuel material in relation to the parent geology of the growing environment and any chemical processes, such as digestion, that the fuel goes through prior to combustion (Kabata-Pendias and Pendias 1984; Obenberger *et al.* 2006; Hagman *et al.* 2013).

The magnetic susceptibility data showed trends in magnetic properties with respect to fuel type (fig. 6). The peat samples have the highest overall magnetic susceptibility (average 676.6 x 10⁻⁸m³kg⁻¹), and the dung samples have the lowest (319.0 x 10⁻⁸m³kg⁻¹). The wood fuels measure approximately 10 % higher than the dung samples (average 348.6 x 10⁻⁸m³kg⁻¹).

The low magnetic susceptibility of the dung ash suggests a low concentration of iron oxides. The intermediate magnetic susceptibility of the wood ash may arise from a higher concentration of iron oxides or increased temperatures. The high values for the peat ash indicate still higher concentrations of iron oxides.

Importantly, the differences in the magnetic susceptibility of the pottery samples can be directly attributed to the use of different fuels and could therefore be considered to be diagnostic. The changes in magnetic susceptibility are influenced by the heat that each fuel can produce and retain. The highest value of magnetic susceptibility amongst the pottery samples is from the pottery

fired in sheep dung, followed by the peat-fired, wood-fired and, finally, lab-fired pottery. The fuels that produce the best insulation prevent cooling from taking place too quickly and provide ideal parameters for magnetising mineral material within the clay as it is converted into ceramic. In this regard, the considerable differences in temperature across a pot as it cools are of significance.

The soil samples again show trends associated with the fuel used (fig. 6). The peat-fired soil has the highest magnetic susceptibility. This is most likely due to the temperature changing the state of magnetisation of the soil minerals and the peat fuels. The soil that has been used for multiple firings also has a high susceptibility. This is most likely due to multiple heating and cooling events as well as varied fuel use.

The SEM images show that dung ash can be distinguished from other fuels on the basis of its appearance, being coarser than the very fine grained peat ash and the lacking of fragments of charcoal and other carbonised inclusions found in wood ash (fig. 7). Sheep dung is also distinguishable from other fuel ashes with the EDS data on account of its high P and Si content and low percentages of C (fig. 8). Peat ash has a greater concentration of Al, Fe, Ca and, Mg than other types of fuels. Wood ash has very high levels of C and low levels of Mg and Na. Although dung ash has the highest measured levels of P, the soil and pottery samples fired in dung have no presence of P. The pottery samples are very similar in respect of the elemental abundances. There are only slight differences in C and Ca. The elemental compositions of the soils are also similar, with the greatest variation being between Si, C, and Al.

All of the pots were fired in wood, peat, or dung, with the exception of the lab-fired control

sample. The firing and soaking times of the firings varied greatly and depended upon the amount of time that each fuel took to achieve the necessary temperature, the amount of fuel used to sustain the combustion and chance factors such as how quickly the fuel caught fire from the embers. In addition to changing the fuels used, the firing environments were also altered to assess the effects of factors including the construction of the firing structure, the presence or absence of firebricks, and the arrangement of the bricks (fig. 9). All of these affect the build-up of residues within the firing environment. Changes in fuel type, the rate of consumption or the fire configuration will all affect the volume and pattern of the deposition of combustion residues.

CONCLUSIONS

Given that dung firing is undertaken around the world today, it is unsurprising that we were able to produce well-fired pots using sheep dung alone. Indeed, in the opinion of the experimental team, sheep dung was the most reliable and easiest to use of the three fuels tested. As a result of our experiments we are able to offer a number of important observations:

1. Despite the lower *average* firing temperatures, the use of sheep dung as fuel resulted in pottery of equally high quality to that fired in wood or peat.
2. Sheep dung firings were shorter than peat or wood firings but the ability of dung to form a 'blanket' of burnt-out fuel after combustion meant that the pots fired in dung cooled more evenly with a reduced risk of cracking. They also exhibited little fire clouding compared to the wood- or peat-fired pots. The relatively rapid temperature rises did not adversely affect the pots if they were well dried and carefully heated before addition to the fire.

Sample	Mass Specific χ_{lf} k/p $\times 10^{-8}$ m ³ kg ⁻¹	% Frequency Dependence (klf-khf/klf) $\times 100$
Multiple firings	665.5	9.2
Peat-fired soil	757.7	9
Wood-fired soil	361.5	8.3
Dung-fired soil	242.2	9.7
Peat ash	843.6	8.3
Wood ash	345.8	8.2
Dung ash	226.7	9.6
Lab-fired pot	250.7	8.2
Peat-fired pot	428.6	6.4
Wood-fired pot	338.6	4.9
Dung-fired pot	488.1	7.4

Fig. 6: Magnetic susceptibility results for samples of soil, ash and pottery. Credit G. Griffin.

Fig. 7: Ashes magnified 300 x. From left to right: wood ash, peat ash, and dung ash. Credit G. Griffin.

Sample	Si %	C %	Al %	Fe %	K %	Ca %	Mg %	Na %	P %
Multiple firings	18.9	11.4	7.9	7.1	1.9	1.9	1	0.5	0.6
Peat-fired soil	9.9	14.7	5.5	8.1	0.9	0.8	1.2	0.1	0.2
Wood-fired soil	14.3	16.2	7.9	10.2	2.6	1.7	0.8	0.1	0.4
Dung-fired soil	24.3	5.8	10.1	8.8	2	0.4	0.8	0.4	0
Peat ash	3.7	13.9	3.5	3.2	0.6	11	10.8	2.3	0.8
Wood ash	5.4	42.3	2.3	1.5	4.1	6.4	1.5	0.4	0.5
Dung ash	11	10.7	0.6	0.6	8.3	9.5	2.6	0.8	6.4
Lab-fired pot	16.3	5.1	7.9	5	2.1	20.4	1	0	0
Peat-fired pot	15.7	6.1	7.5	4.6	2	18.3	0.9	0	0
Wood-fired pot	16.1	8.5	6.8	5.3	2.1	18.5	0.8	0.2	0
Dung-fired pot	16	7.3	7	4.9	2.2	16.1	0.8	0	0

Fig. 8: SEM/EDS data showing the percentage of selected elements in soil ash and pottery samples. Credit G. Griffin.

Fig. 9: Variations in the placement of firebricks (compare to Fig. 2 and 4). Credit M. Copper.

For these reasons we believe that sheep dung would have provided a potentially valuable source of fuel in prehistoric Europe and that archaeologists should consider this when excavating or interpreting burnt features. However, it is also important to consider factors that are hard to measure when assessing the probability that different types of fuel may have been used. These include:

1. The ease and speed with which a fuel source can be collected, dried and stored.
2. The times of year in which the fuel is available and how this fits in with other economic activities.
3. How quickly a resource is renewed and what impact its collection has on the local environment.
4. The social status assigned to the use of different combustibles.
5. The difference that the acquisition of skill can make to the quality of the pots produced.

From a technical point of view we would suggest that using just one or two thermocouples, or averaging temperatures readings, gives an inaccurate picture of the firing process. Temperatures taken at different points in the fire, and particularly inside vessels, provide a clearer picture of what is happening during a firing.

In respect of identifying the use of sheep dung in an archaeological context, we would stress the importance of combining different analytical techniques (the ‘toolkit’ approach). Multiple methods pointing to the same conclusion add strength to the conclusion reached. Our post-firing analysis suggests that the use of sheep dung as a pot firing fuel leaves a number of diagnostic traces, notably:

1. The pottery, ash and soil samples from the dung firings exhibit a low magnetic susceptibility in comparison to those associated with wood and peat firings.
2. Sheep dung is distinguishable from other fuel ashes with the EDS data on account of its high P and Si content and low concentration of C.
3. In comparison to dung ash, peat ash is characterised by its very fine structure and wood ash by the presence of fragments of charcoal and other carbonised matter.

The methods applied here are viable to carry out in archaeological settings. However, this research demonstrates the need for multiple approaches. One method is not capable of creating a comprehensive picture on its own. There is a need to create robust datasets built upon corroborative methods such as SEM/EDS and magnetic susceptibility. It is also beneficial to have soil, ash, and pottery samples to fully identify the use of dung as a fuel.

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DÉCEMBRE 2021

En 2021, l'Association Pour l'Expérimentation et la Recherche Archéologique (APERA) inaugure le premier numéro de son Bulletin annuel. Ce Bulletin publie des articles originaux en français ou anglais au sujet de l'expérimentation en archéologie. Ces écrits sont consacrés aussi bien à des projets et protocoles expérimentaux qu'à la diffusion de synthèses et de résultats.

Ce 1^{er} numéro du Bulletin est l'occasion de publier les actes de la Journée Thématique de l'association qui s'est tenue le 4 juin 2021 à l'Institut d'Art et d'Archéologie. Cette Journée Thématique internationale, sous la modération de Haris Procopiou (Professeure, Université Paris 1), a réuni dix communicants étudiants, professionnels de l'archéologie préventive ou médiateurs en archéologie. Centrée sur les apports de l'expérimentation à la recherche archéologique sur la Protohistoire (Néolithique - âge du Bronze - âge du Fer), cette journée s'est articulée autour de problématiques variées, mettant en lumière l'interdisciplinarité des travaux expérimentaux actuels : apports ethnographiques et sociologiques, analyses physiques et chimiques, études numériques tridimensionnelles. Elle a été l'occasion d'échanger sur le potentiel et les limites de la démarche expérimentale, ainsi que de discuter de l'importance de la médiation archéologique.

Illustration page de couverture :
*Incendie d'une reconstitution expérimentale d'un
bâtiment néolithique en 2020, Mézeray, Sarthe.*
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